

ISTANBUL
INTERNATIONAL MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH
CONGRESS -V
July 9-II, 2023 | Istanbul, Türkiye

THE BOOK OF FULL TEXTS

Edited by
Prof. Dr. Osman ERKMEN
Gulnaz GAFUROVA

ISBN: 978-625-367-198-3

INTERNATIONAL ISTANBUL MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONGRESS-V

THE BOOK OF FULL TEXTS

EDITED BY

Prof. Dr. Osman ERKMEN

Gulnaz GAFUROVA

By

IKSAD Institute

All rights of this book belong IKSAD Publishing House

Authors of chapters are responsible both ethically and juridically

www.istanbulkongresi.org

Issued: 25.07.2023

ISBN: 978-625-367-198-3

CONGRESS'S IDENTIFICATION
İSTANBUL International Modern Scientific Research Congress-V

DATE AND PLACE
9-11 July 2023
İstanbul, TÜRKİYE
(FACE TO FACE AND ONLINE)

ORGANIZATION
IKSAD Institute

HEAD OF CONGRESS
Prof. Dr. Osman ERKMEN

COORDINATOR
Gulnaz GAFUROVA

NUMBER OF ACCEPTED PAPERS 229
NUMBER OF REJECTED PAPERS 15
TOTAL NUMBER OF PAPERS FROM TÜRKİYE 112
TOTAL NUMBER OF INTERNATIONAL PARTICIPANTS 117

PARTICIPATION COUNTRIES

Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Uzbekistan, Algeria, India, Italy, Portugal, Indonesia,
Vietnam, Albania, Mexico, Romania, Nigeria, UK, Canada, France, Georgia,
Kyrgyzstan

EVALUATION PROCESS
All applications have undergone a double-blind peer review process

SCIENCE AND ADVISORY BOARD

- Dr. Şükrü Karataş - İstanbul Arel University
 Dr. Mehmet Pala – Halich University
 Dr. Yeşim Müge Şahin - İstanbul Arel University
 Dr. Ayşe Erkmen – Gaziantep University
 Dr. Fitnat Şule Şakar - İstanbul Arel University
 Dr. Dilek Özçelik Ersü - İstanbul Arel University
 Dr. Özlem Persil Özkan - İstanbul Arel University
 Dr. İlkay Turhan Kara - İstanbul Arel University
 Dr. A. Beril TUĞRUL- Istanbul Technical University
 Dr. Aparna SRIVATAVA- Noida University
 Dr. Gülzar İBRAHİMOVA- Baku Eurasia University Italy
 Dr. Rada NOVAKOVIC- National Research Council,
 Dr. C. VIJAI- St. Peter Institute of Higher Education and Research
 Dr. Dipanvita PAL- Burdwan University and Technology
 Dr. Ethem İlhan ŞAHİN- Adana Alparslan Türkeş Science
 University
 Dr. Lech Kościelak- University of Warsaw
 Dr. Terane NAGHIYEVA- Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University
 Dr. Muhammad AKRAM- Government College Faisalabad University
 Dr. Mustafa Bayram- Gaziantep University
 Dr. Çiğdem Aykaç- Gaziantep University
 Dr. Hidayet Sağlam- Kilis 7 Aralık University
 Dr. Faruk Bozoğlu- KTO Karatay University
 Dr. Hüseyin Erten- Çukurova University
 Dr. Arzu Çağrı Mehmetoğlu- Sakarya University
 Dr. Muhammet Arıcı- Yıldız University
 Dr. Osman Sağdıç- Yıldız University
 Dr. Yeşim Ekinci- Yeditepe University
 Dr. Nükhet N. Zorba- Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University
 Dr. Mihriban Koruklu- Uludag University
 Dr. İrem Korkmaz- Marmara University University
 Dr. Emre Ertan- Marmara University
 Dr. Fatih Özbey- University of Health Sciences
 Dr. Hasan Yetim- İstanbul Sabahattin Zaim
 Dr. Çiğdem Soysal- Gaziantep University
 Dr. Ahmet Hilmi Çön- Pamukkale University
 Dr. Dilek Heperkan- İstanbul Aydın University
 Dr. Fatma ÇAPAN- Gaziantep University

ANOTHER PANDEMIC DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: "DOMESTIC VIOLENCE"

Gizem ŞAHİN

Üsküdar University, Faculty of Engineering and Natural Sciences, Department of Forensic Sciences

ORCID ID: 0009-0008-4888-5756

Security and Forensic Sciences Expert / Görkem Ardacan TAN

Üsküdar University, Institute of Addiction and Forensic Sciences, Department of Criminal Justice

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3050-0095

1. ABSTRACT

For the first time in decades, a pandemic has affected more than 200 countries. "Stay home, save lives" has been shown to mitigate the effects of COVID-19, but efforts to de-stress health systems have had unintended consequences for domestic violence. According to the World Health Organization, approximately 1 in 3 women have experienced physical and/or sexual violence by an intimate partner in their lifetime. Domestic violence is a pandemic-added global public health problem with huge social and economic costs. The incidence of domestic violence can be exacerbated in times of crisis, high unemployment and social stress. Isolation also has the potential to increase domestic violence.

Domestic violence calls for service in 14 major US cities saw a 9.7% increase in domestic violence calls in the first five weeks after the start of widespread social distancing, and a 7.5% increase in domestic violence calls for service in the 12 weeks following this period. In the UK, the National Domestic Abuse Helpline saw a 25% increase in calls and online messages after the curfew began. In Cyprus, people were asked to stay at home when the first Covid case was detected, and phone numbers increased by over 30% shortly after calls to the violence helpline. Increased unemployment during the COVID-19 pandemic and decisions to stay at home have led victims to spend longer periods at home with perpetrators, making them less likely to flee in violent situations. The United Nations Secretary-General has also called for this. He called on all governments to take measures to address the alarming global increase in domestic violence. The Secretary-General added that all governments should make the prevention of violence against women "an essential part of national response plans for Covid-19".

This important issue has remained in the background during the pandemic, and mostly no policy has been implemented. In countries that did, they did not plan ahead. Among the countries that have implemented policies, Spain, for example, imposed penalties for violating quarantine rules and relaxed restrictions on women if they leave their homes due to violence. The Scottish government has pledged over GBP 5 million in grants for continued access to support services for organizations working to address abuse during the Covid pandemic. Considering this period, it has been concluded that in times of global difficulties, studies should be carried out in cooperation with many groups to prevent domestic violence. Our research aim is to present the measures to be taken and plans to be made for domestic violence in a possible global crisis in the future. Our study method is to comprehensively gather the researches that report the situation of domestic violence in the literature during this period. Based on these researches, it is aimed to be more conscious and reduce domestic violence by offering recommendations from our suggestions and inferences.

Keywords: Domestic Violence, Covid-19, Pandemic, Isolation, Stay Home

1. GİRİŞ

Modern societies are facing more diseases, accidents and disasters every day than in the past. All these mean risk and those who are more exposed to risk are the poor, women, the elderly and children (Demircioğlu, 2021). It is known that such chaotic events affect domestic peace. For example, a four-fold increase in rates of gender-based violence was reported among displaced women in Mississippi after Hurricane Katrina. More globally, sudden increases in domestic violence have been seen after the 2004 Indian Ocean earthquake and tsunami and the Black Saturday bushfires in Australia. Disasters such as hurricanes, earthquakes, floods, oil spills, epidemics increase in the acute phase and it is important to remember that domestic violence fluctuations usually continue for years during the recovery period (de Lima, Alves, de Oliveira, de Oliveira, Barbosa, Marcene, & de Oliveira, 2020). The COVID-19 epidemic, which relapsed in Wuhan, China in December 2019 and then spread to the whole world, affected the whole flow of life, and the contagion spread with worry and anxiety (Demircioğlu, 2021). The promise of "stay home, save lives" has been shown to reduce the risk of transmission of the virus, but efforts not to stress health systems have had unintended social consequences for domestic violence (Krishnakumar, & Verma, 2021). Women have battled a shadow epidemic inside their homes (Krishnakumar, & Verma, 2021). Because some houses are not safe. According to 2013 data, approximately one-third of women worldwide have experienced physical and/or sexual violence by their close partners in their lifetime (Berniell, & Facchini, 2021). In explaining the impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on the family institution, it is necessary to define violence first. Considering its close relationship with spiritual processes, it can be understood that violence can vary from society to society, culture to culture, and that it is one of the most primitive forms of behavior on the axis of the notion of "power". Violence is divided into physical and psychological. Physical violence is the most common and easily recognized type of violence. It involves the conscious use of force. Injuring, hitting, slapping, pushing, punching, hitting with an object, killing, damaging the person's body temporarily or permanently, hitting with a weapon can be given as examples. Psychological violence, on the other hand, is violence applied to maintain its dominance over the individual by oppressing the individual and by exploiting his feelings and emotional needs. Its purpose is to gain respect and strength by giving fear to the family member (Demircioğlu, 2021).

Domestic violence is a global public health problem in addition to crises such as the pandemic, which have huge social and economic costs. At the same time, the World Health Organization recognizes violence against women as a public health burden (Anurudran, Yared, Comrie, Harrison, & Burke, 2020). Domestic violence can also contribute to reduced economic productivity and increased medical and judicial costs (Leigh, Peña, Anurudran, & Pai, 2023). Domestic violence is also referred to as intimate partner violence, relationship violence or dating abuse in the literature (Lima, Alves, de Oliveira, de Oliveira, Barbosa, Marcene, & de Oliveira, 2020). The incidence of domestic violence may be exacerbated during crises, times of high unemployment, social stress and uncertainty.

The situation has become even more serious during the COVID-19 pandemic as unemployment rises and lockdowns have made victims spend longer periods of time at home with abusers and less likely to run away (Berniell, & Facchini, 2021). There has been an increase in domestic violence cases after closure throughout the world in this process. Globally, he calls this a "double epidemic". (Lima, Alves, de Oliveira, de Oliveira, Barbosa, Marcene, & de Oliveira, 2020).

The situation has become even more serious during the COVID-19 pandemic as unemployment rises and lockdowns have made victims spend longer periods of time at home with abusers and less likely to run away (Berniell, & Facchini, 2021). There has been an increase in domestic violence cases after closure throughout the world in this process. Globally, he calls this a

"double epidemic". (Lima, Alves, de Oliveira, de Oliveira, Barbosa, Marcene, & de Oliveira, 2020).

While children who are especially affected by traumas at home have difficulty in controlling and expressing their emotions, they can also become a perpetrator of violence with the suppression of emotions and the transmission of violence between generations in adulthood. Such dynamics can lead to destructive aggression and intergenerational transmission of trauma and violence (Mazza, Marano, Lai, Janiri, & Sani, 2020). In order to prevent these damages, domestic violence should be kept in the foreground in the event of a possible crisis. While staying at home promises a virus-free life, it should not promise a life of vulnerability and violence at home (Krishnakumar, & Verma, 2021). However, most countries lack the necessary information to contain this situation and implement swift public policies. (Berniell, & Facchini, 2021). It is necessary to be prepared for a possible second crisis. Our research aim is to guide the measures and plans to be taken against domestic violence in a future global crisis. Our method of study, we made use of literature records during the COVID pandemic period. It is to analyze the situation of domestic violence and present our conclusions and recommendations in a comprehensive way to the relevant authorities and the scientific world.

2. FINDINGS

2.1. THE STATUS OF DOMESTIC VIOLENCE DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC PROCESS

Even under normal conditions, approximately 30% of women worldwide are exposed to intimate partner violence during their lifetime (Gibson, J. (2020). The World Health Organization has pointed out that the decrease in access to services and social environment during the COVID-19 period will increase violence against women. For example, In cases where family members spend time in close contact, it is predicted that the domestic workload will increase as a result of a member's economic or job loss, and the closure of schools, and that economic abuse will intensify as a result of which the livelihood will become difficult. It is seen that the place where it is seen is in Istanbul, and according to the data of the Istanbul Police Department, the only crime that increased in the rate of public order crimes in Turkey during the pandemic process was domestic violence by 38.2% (Demircioğlu, 2021). Compared to this, it increased by 30-36% in France, 25% in Argentina, 10-35% in the United States, 40-50% in Brazil, and applications to hotlines due to violence by 20% in Spain and England. It was stated that it increased by 25% in (Demircioğlu, 2021). Rates of domestic violence have increased in many countries, such as Brazil, Germany, Italy, China, the United Kingdom, the United States, and Australia.

We compared domestic violence calls for service in 14 major US cities before and after the initiation of social distancing. In the first five weeks after social distancing began, calls for domestic violence increased by 9.7% (Leslie, & Wilson, 2020). An online survey of 15,000 Australian women found that 4.6% had experienced physical or sexual violence; 5.8% were found to experience compulsive controlling and 11.6% experienced at least one form of abusive or controlling behavior (Indu, Vijayan, Tharayil, Ayirolimeethal, & Vidyadharan, 2021).

It reported a 60% increase in emergency calls on violence against women by its close partners in Europe. A study of Ethiopian women found that nearly one in four women had experienced any form of domestic violence during the COVID-19 pandemic (Krishnakumar, & Verma, 2021) In the UK, the National Domestic Abuse Hotline reported on calls and calls after the curfew began. noticed a 25% increase in online messages. Calls to the violence hotline increased by over 30% after the lockdown in Cyprus during the pandemic.

An 8.3% increase in physical domestic violence (domestic or intimate partner violence) experienced by young people aged 18-26 was identified during the 2020 COVID-19 restrictions in Peru (Porter, Favara, M., Sánchez, & Scott , 2021). Spain has relaxed the restriction on women if they leave their homes due to violence. Organizations in the UK have called for

special police powers to combat domestic violence. A union group in Italy demanded that the perpetrator, not the victim, be kept in a shelter during the epidemic. Police forces in Greece have invested in public campaigns to raise awareness of domestic violence during the epidemic and strategies to assist victims (Ghoshal, 2020).

2.2. THINGS THAT CAN BE DONE IN FIGHTING DOMESTIC VIOLENCE IN ACRISIS

It is important to get information in communication with doctors and other health personnel in the detection of domestic violence, and at the same time, it has the chance to observe the trauma of domestic violence, including the filiation teams. Early intervention and referral to a security unit or lawyer can prevent an abusive situation from worsening with more intense violence, saving lives. In the UK, for example, access to emergency care is via phone or video to avoid contact. Of course, the first and foremost concern is the patient's safety. If the patient is with the perpetrator, disclosure will not be possible, and it will put the victim in greater danger. When questioning the etiology, the patient should be asked to answer "yes" or "no" whether it is safe to talk. If the answer is 'no', ask if she feels safe or in danger. If the victim is available, this is the appropriate time and it is necessary to question the cause of the injury, how, when and where it occurred. At the same time, law enforcement personnel can go along with the filiation teams who come to visit the house. It is important for the safety of the noticing healthcare professional. Dentists are the occupational group that will play an important role in another determination. Dentists are therefore in a good position to observe and detect injuries to the head, eyes, ears, neck, face, mouth and teeth. With the relaxation of restrictions during the pandemic period, a dental examination is important.

When domestic violence involves physical assault, the face is a very common target, with 65% to 95% of attacks occurring on the face. Dentists, oral and maxillofacial surgeons all have a critical role in identifying patients who present with dental and facial injuries and referring them to specialist institutions. Because the dental visit is unaccompanied, the dental setting is a unique and advantageous location for research on domestic violence (Coulthard, Hutchison, Bell, Coulthard, & Kennedy, 2020).

Private health services may be required. WHO research shows that those who have experienced violence or abuse are twice as likely to have an abortion, and this experience nearly doubles their likelihood of becoming depressed (Ghoshal, 2020). Pregnant women in Iran go to health centers to receive health services throughout their pregnancy, and therefore, it is vital to screen pregnant women for domestic violence, to make appropriate interventions, and to improve the quality of life of abused women in these centers, as in other centers.

In other words, these determinations and inquiries are possible during hospital controls of pregnant women (Naghizadeh, Mirghafourvand, & Mohammadirad, 2021). A decrease in emergency room visits due to sexual assault and domestic violence has been found during COVID 19. This is because the priority is to fight the corona virus (Muldoon, Denize, Talarico, Fell, Sobiesiak, Heimerl, & Sampsel, 2021). Sexual violence may also increase during quarantine. Some regions are 1.5 times more likely to contract HIV (Ghoshal, 2020).

India has seen an increase in porn use and sales of condoms and sex toys, reflecting an increase in sexual activity and thus indirectly an increased likelihood of sexual infringement. The fact that women are very tired with the increasing care burden may cause them to be forced to have sex (Adibelli, Sümen, & Teskereci, 2021).

Also, as Health authorities are busy controlling the spread of the virus, perpetrators can often harass without question (Malathesh, Das, & Chatterjee, 2020). Tracking domestic violence should first of all maintain a database prior to such disasters. Because if there is a history of violence, an increase in domestic violence should be expected. The risk is increased if there is a history of violence other than those who have not reported violence before (Porter, Favara, Sánchez, & Scott, 2021). Such families should be monitored in such cases, that is, they should

be contacted or visited. Advertisements should be made about domestic violence telephone numbers, police stations and the activity of websites providing 24/7 service. It is recommended that the security and crime-fighting units monitor violence by phone and especially by text message. In addition, telematics systems or resorting to legal remedies can be implemented. Data can be collected in places frequented by women, such as neighborhood pharmacies and supermarkets (de Souza Santos, Bittencourt, de Moraes Malinverni, Kisberi, de França Vilaça, & Iwamura, 2022). For example, Spanish pharmacies have been identified as contact points where the victim can leave a message for his/her rescue if he/she cannot call the helpline numbers (Ghoshal, 2020). Institutions serving victims of domestic violence must explore new and expanded community partnerships. Many postal workers, garbage collectors, food delivery personnel, and home repairmen roam neighborhoods during the global crisis, staying close to homes, may have opportunities to detect domestic violence and report their concerns to the appropriate authorities (Campbell, 2020). He has a duty to society. If we know that any family member, relative or neighbor is a victim of domestic violence, we should keep an eye on each other, even during social distancing. Governments, non-governmental organizations, community-based organizations, voluntary organizations and religious leaders should use various media and platforms to raise awareness (Sifat, 2020). We must make citizens aware of the currently increasing risk of domestic violence, encourage them to control their neighbors, friends and family, and teach them to report to the appropriate authorities in any case (Campbell, 2020). Communication should always be active with victims. Several common barriers to access were seen in the literature, including a lack of clear communication by victims about what resources were used in the pandemic.

Information on which services are open during the pandemic could not be given. It became difficult for the victims to make a healthy phone call (Leigh, Peña, Anurudran, & Pai, 2023). Therefore, creative new strategies are also needed. It will be easier to report complaints online. Media and digital networks can be used for domestic violence awareness and complaint reporting (Hall, & Tucker, 2020).

The provision of shelters, hotlines, public services for governments, digital services via text-based messaging will enable the victim to raise the complaint in a safe manner. Victims should have 24-hour access to advice, shelter and helplines (Yari, Zahednezhad, Gheshlagh, & Kurdi, 2021). The Internet is very important in detecting and monitoring domestic violence. Looking at a panel of eleven countries in a sample study, an average of 31% increase in searches for domestic violence was seen when comparing five years of Google search data on domestic violence-related topics to data after stay-at-home orders were implemented.

The peak of this increase occurred on average 5 weeks after the start of the quarantine. This study offers the following advantage: the amount of this data can be compared in different geographies, free of charge, quickly and daily. It is also an extremely important resource on online platforms, such as Twitter trend data, as it may contain what is not reported in surveys or administrative records. It seems that online searches can be an extra source of information for governments (Berniell, & Facchini, 2021). For this, there must be internet access everywhere. Refuge, the charity against domestic violence, reported a 700% increase in calls in a single day during the pandemic. Calls and people to the helpline increased by an average of 66% per week, and visits to the website increased by 950% during the Covid-19 pandemic (Gibson, J. (2020). While the target for downloading the KADES application by 917 thousand people was 1 million in December 2020, it was seen that the number of downloads of the KADES application was 1 million 174 thousand on December 20, 2020. Downloading such applications shows the presence of danger and the precautions taken by individuals (Demircioğlu, 2021). In just one week of the lockdown in India, the National Commission on Women in India has doubled the number of complaints, which is worrying as the complaints are received via email, women do not have access to emails and cannot use the mail due to the

lockdown (Ghoshal, 2020). This is necessary because domestic violence more frequently victimizes poor, rural and low-educated women.

There are examples where women living in rural areas were found to be more at risk. In a study investigating the vulnerabilities of raped and beaten women, low schooling, black race, and younger age were observed as common characteristics (Kofman, & Garfin, 2020).

Overcrowded families with low socioeconomic status are particularly vulnerable to violence (Øverlien, 2020). In the absence of poverty and financial freedom, coping measures are necessary despite the barriers to breaking up with abusive and violent relationships. It is extremely important to create accessible institutions, university extensions that will develop clear educational materials for the public (de Souza Santos, Bittencourt, de Moraes Malinverni, Kisberi, de França Vilaça, & Iwamura, 2022). Poverty can be prevented through education. This will be a permanent solution to prevent domestic violence and violence will not be allowed by obtaining individual freedom. Financial independence is a known protective factor against domestic violence (Bright, Burton, & Kosky, (2020). (Yari, Zahednezhad, Gheshlagh, & Kurdi, 2021). a combination of these three emotions, especially in patriarchal cultures, often leads to perverse violence against the dependents at hand, namely the elderly, children and women in the household (Ghoshal, 2020).

For example, in the first five weeks of curfew, over 26 million too many Americans have lost their jobs. The United Nations Interagency Standing Committee has warned that 94% of all working women work in the informal sector and will bear the brunt of being without an income. This is one of the things that can be done for future generations, while in the current situation social assistance is needed. A similar financial threat due to the virus creates uncertainty, frustrations and stresses in the men of the household, just like in a pressure cooker. A combination of these three emotions, especially in patriarchal cultures, often leads to perverse violence against the dependents at hand, namely the elderly, children and women in the household (Ghoshal, 2020). For example, more than 26 million Americans lost their jobs in the first five weeks of the curfew. The United Nations Inter-Agency Standing Committee warned that 94% of all working women work in the informal sector and will bear the burden of no income.

Since women are more likely to be in the informal sector, they will be the most economically affected by COVID-19 (Ghoshal, 2020). Individuals who did not lose their jobs also experienced a decline in income. Low income and unemployment are known risk factors for domestic violence. More specifically, male unemployment affects domestic violence. Economic factors make the victim financially dependent on the abuser (Bright, Burton, & Kosky, (2020). Funds can be set aside or insurance can be provided to prevent financial hardship in families.

It should cover strategies to provide social and health support to vulnerable victims. Shelters and other response services did not work in the same way due to social distancing measures (Bright, Burton, & Kosky, (2020). Shelters and shelters should not be closed in such cases. Media should be informed that they are not closed. Safe havens play a key role for victims of domestic violence (Øverlien, 2020). During the coronavirus crisis, some shelter staff expressed concern about silence. They seem to believe that being at home during the day increases the risk of violence and abuse.

The lives of children and adolescents have been particularly affected by the pandemic. This is because closed schools and daycare centers mean spending longer with parents who are prone to violence (Øverlien, 2020). In an online survey conducted at the University of Michigan (562 parents), 52% of parents reported that lockdown and financial concerns have affected their parenting. While 61% of these parents reported yelling or screaming at their children since the beginning of the pandemic, 19% reported yelling more than usual and 11% reported beating their child several times.

The federal state of Maine (USA) has seen a significant 32% drop in the number of reports since schools were closed. In February, 22% of reports of suspected child abuse and neglect were reported by kindergarten and school teachers, while in March this percentage dropped to 7% due to the difficulty of communicating with students. The method of communication through electronic devices, currently recommended by professionals, can be very dangerous and unsafe for victims, as it is almost impossible to get the child to communicate privately with a professional, which makes it difficult to detect and report abuse (Roje Đapić, Buljan Flander, & Prijatelj, 2020). Rising child abuse can be the "irreversible scarring of a generation". Disclosure and detection of child abuse also becomes more difficult in times of crisis (Roje Đapić, Buljan Flander, & Prijatelj, 2020). The follow-up of a family with a history of violence should not be neglected, no matter what the catastrophe.

Otherwise, the next generation will be neglected. Among countries that have implemented such policies, France has decided to open its hotels as safe havens for those seeking protection from domestic violence (Ghoshal, 2020).

Psychological counseling and support services should be provided. In addition, psychiatric treatments should not be interrupted. Research from previous pandemics shows that the length of the quarantine period is associated with the degree of psychological consequences such as depression and stress (Bright, Burton, & Kosky, (2020). Lockdowns and restrictions have also been linked to higher rates of domestic violence, drug misuse and anxiety, major depression, suicide and unmet mental health needs (Anurudran, Yared, Comrie, Harrison, & Burke, 2020). According to a study conducted in the United Kingdom, there is also a tendency to self-harm as a result of all the challenging factors during the pandemic.

In the first 5 weeks after the Covid-19 lockdown at King's College Hospital in South London, trauma admissions showed an increase in both self-harm and penetrating injuries due to domestic violence. Penetrating neck injuries are reminiscent of suicidal intentions and psychiatric disorders. As can be understood, follow-up of risky groups and psychological counseling and treatment should not be interrupted during such periods (Olding, Zisman, Olding, & Fan, 2021). A Spanish study on the COVID-19 pandemic reported depressive syndrome in 39.9% of women. In a study of Tunisian women, 57.3% of women had extremely severe depression and anxiety. During the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown, when nationwide isolation was implemented in India, 10.0% of married women aged 18-55 years reported depressive symptoms, 7.2% reported mild anxiety symptoms, and 66.6% reported moderate perceived stress. 25.8% of the population had experienced at least one form of domestic violence during the pandemic and lockdown (Indu, Vijayan, Tharayil, Ayirolimeethal, & Vidyadharan, 2021). Myhill and Hohl (2019). In his study, he found that the majority of perpetrators of domestic violence (53.3%) had substance abuse or mental illness. In addition, domestic violence perpetrators who abuse or neglect animals that can be considered individuals in the home are more likely to have mental illness and/or substance abuse (Campbell, 2020). Drug addiction also often increases social isolation, leading to victimization and greater susceptibility to offending (Bright, Burton, & Kosky, 2020). For this reason, psychological counseling and treatments should not be interrupted. Even if it is online therapy, treatments should not be interrupted.

We have already mentioned alcohol and drug addiction among the addictions motivating domestic violence. Restricting the marketing of alcohol and drugs is recommended (de Souza Santos, Bittencourt, de Moraes Malinverni, Kisberi, de França Vilaça, & Iwamura, 2022). As countries around the world have begun to impose lockdowns to contain the spread of the novel coronavirus, there have been countries that have imposed restrictions on the sale and purchase of alcohol. Countries such as South Africa, Thailand, Greenland and Sri Lanka either imposed a blanket ban or restricted it to specific locations with a high prevalence of domestic abuse. Alcohol shops were also closed for business in India when lockdowns were imposed. It is

important to note, however, that alcohol consumption can be one of the reasons for resorting to domestic violence. But at the same time, domestic violence can also be caused by the abuser experiencing withdrawal symptoms, not only because of alcohol consumption (Krishnakumar, & Verma, 2021).

The solution here is not to ban alcohol consumption, because this would lead to an increase in the sale of illicit/illegal alcohol, i.e. under the stairs. Even if alcohol consumption declines slightly, it can be said that people continue to consume alcohol by resorting to illegitimate means (Krishnakumar, & Verma, 2021).

When it comes to drug addiction, addicts who cannot obtain illegal drugs due to the stress and restriction created by the pandemic may resort to extreme violence with the symptom of withdrawal. Again, reporting these individuals to the relevant authorities may initiate their treatment (Bright, Burton, & Kosky, 2020).

The interest and activity of the security forces in domestic violence cases is important in such periods. Lack of police power was seen in some literature findings. For example, in one case, a survivor of domestic violence started running through the narrow streets of a slum when she was beaten by her husband, but could not escape due to the curfew and police barricade. These events reflected how the absence of an important guardian, the police, facilitated domestic violence during the pandemic shutdown.

It is the official protective police capable of dealing with any violent crime. During the pandemic, most of the police force was on the ground and tightly engaged in the enforcement and monitoring of pandemic restrictions (Krishnakumar, & Verma, 2021). Law enforcement officers need to have more operational tools to reach everywhere such as district and village areas and take appropriate action (Sifat, 2020). Also, looking historically at more than 1 million pre-sales across the US in March 2020 compared to March 2019, research firm Small Arms Analytics & Forecasting (SAAF) predicted a 91% increase in pistol purchases over the same 2 years. Having more unsafe guns in homes likely makes domestic violence incidents more deadly. Firearms can be easily accessible to curious children if not stored properly, they are risky. Security units should also monitor these, and gun sales may be restricted during such periods (Duncan, Weaver, Zakrison, Joseph, Campbell, Christmas, & Bulger, 2020).

3. CONCLUSIONS and RECOMMENDATION

Increasing domestic violence in crises has been characterized by many experts as 'Intimate Terrorism' (Taub, 2020). We must not let domestic violence remain in the shadows (Campbell, 2020). Every state needs to prepare a national guideline on how to deal with increasing cases of domestic and intimate partner violence (Ghoshal, 2020). Such research is instructive to determine how public health interventions and government policies can best support survivors during future disasters where similar measures may be necessary (Leigh, Peña, Anurudran, & Pai, 2023).

Staff and resources to deal specifically with single family violence response should be increased. Collaboration and coordination should be ensured. Across the country, clinical experts, researchers, advocates, policymakers, and government agencies are working tirelessly to reduce the current fallout.

Communication with society's problems must always be active, no matter what. Practices and contingency plans should be prepared so that victims can get a quick response. Involve the community in combating domestic violence through education and awareness-raising. It is up to governments to implement such recommendations. The right policies must be put in place by governments.

With the threat of a second wave of crisis, it is imperative that efforts are made to ensure that as many as possible are integrated into the continuous response and improvement of work to protect against domestic violence (Berniell, & Facchini, 2021). We dream of a world where justice, security and peace do not go on vacation (Uzobo, & Ayinmoro, 2023).

SOURCE

1. Demircioğlu, S. (2021). Türkiye’de Covid-19 Salgısının Aile İçi Şiddete Etkisi. Uluslararası Sosyal Hizmet Araştırmaları Dergisi, 1 (2), 53-68 . Retrieved from <https://dergipark.org.tr/pub/jswrpub/issue/65463/1011722>
2. de Lima, C. A., Alves, P. M. R., de Oliveira, C. J. B., de Oliveira, T. R. N., Barbosa, K. B., Marcene, H. C., & de Oliveira, S. V. (2020). COVID-19: isolations, quarantines and domestic violence in rural areas. *SciMedicine Journal*, 2(1), 44-45.
DOI: [10.28991/SciMedJ-2020-0201-7](https://doi.org/10.28991/SciMedJ-2020-0201-7)
3. Krishnakumar, A., & Verma, S. (2021). Understanding domestic violence in India during COVID-19: a routine activity approach. *Asian journal of criminology*, 16(1), 19-35.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11417-020-09340-1>
4. Berniell, I., & Facchini, G. (2021). COVID-19 lockdown and domestic violence: Evidence from internet-search behavior in 11 countries. *European Economic Review*, 136, 103775.
doi: [10.1016/j.euroecorev.2021.103775](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.euroecorev.2021.103775)
5. Anurudran, A., Yared, L., Comrie, C., Harrison, K., & Burke, T. (2020). Domestic violence amid COVID-19. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*, 150(2), 255-256.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ijgo.13247>
6. Leigh, J. K., Peña, L. D., Anurudran, A., & Pai, A. (2023). “Are you safe to talk?": Perspectives of service providers on experiences of domestic violence during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Family Violence*, 38(2), 215-225.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10896-022-00359-9>
7. Mazza, M., Marano, G., Lai, C., Janiri, L., & Sani, G. (2020). Danger in danger: Interpersonal violence during COVID-19 quarantine. *Psychiatry research*, 289, 113046.
doi: [10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113046](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113046)
8. Gibson, J. (2020). Domestic violence during COVID-19: the GP role. *The British Journal of General Practice*, 70(696), 340.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp20X710477>
9. Leslie, E., & Wilson, R. (2020). Sheltering in place and domestic violence: Evidence from calls for service during COVID-19. *Journal of public economics*, 189, 104241.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2020.104241>
10. Indu, P. V., Vijayan, B., Tharayil, H. M., Ayirolimeethal, A., & Vidyadharan, V. (2021). Domestic violence and psychological problems in married women during COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown: a community-based survey. *Asian journal of psychiatry*, 64, 102812.
doi: [10.1016/j.ajp.2021.102812](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2021.102812)
11. Campbell, A. M. (2020). An increasing risk of family violence during the Covid-19 pandemic: Strengthening community collaborations to save lives. *Forensic science international: reports*, 2, 100089.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsir.2020.100089>
12. Porter, C., Favara, M., Sánchez, A., & Scott, D. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 lockdowns on physical domestic violence: Evidence from a list randomization experiment. *SSM-population health*, 14, 100792.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmph.2021.100792>
13. Ghoshal, R. (2020). Twin public health emergencies: Covid-19 and domestic violence. *Indian J Med Ethics*, 5(3), 195-199.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.20529/IJME.2020.056>

14. Coulthard, P., Hutchison, I., Bell, J. A., Coulthard, I. D., & Kennedy, H. (2020). COVID-19, domestic violence and abuse, and urgent dental and oral and maxillofacial surgery care. *British dental journal*, 228(12), 923-926.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41415-020-1709-1>
15. Naghizadeh, S., Mirghafourvand, M., & Mohammadirad, R. (2021). Domestic violence and its relationship with quality of life in pregnant women during the outbreak of COVID-19 disease. *BMC pregnancy and childbirth*, 21, 1-10.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-021-03579-x>
16. Muldoon, K. A., Denize, K. M., Talarico, R., Fell, D. B., Sobiesiak, A., Heimerl, M., & Sampsel, K. (2021). COVID-19 pandemic and violence: rising risks and decreasing urgent care-seeking for sexual assault and domestic violence survivors. *BMC medicine*, 19(1), 1-9.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-020-01897-z>
17. Adibelli, D., Sümen, A., & Teskereci, G. (2021). Domestic violence against women during the Covid-19 pandemic: Turkey sample. *Health care for women international*, 42(3), 335-350.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/07399332.2021.1885408>
18. Malathesh, B. C., Das, S., & Chatterjee, S. S. (2020). COVID-19 and domestic violence against women. *Asian journal of psychiatry*, 53, 102227.
doi: [10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102227](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102227)
19. de Souza Santos, D., Bittencourt, E. A., de Moraes Malinverni, A. C., Kisberi, J. B., de França Vilaça, S., & Iwamura, E. S. M. (2022). Domestic violence against women during the Covid-19 pandemic: A scoping review. *Forensic science international: reports*, 5, 100276.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsir.2022.100276>
20. Sifat, R. I. (2020). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on domestic violence in Bangladesh. *Asian journal of psychiatry*, 53, 102393.
doi: [10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102393](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102393)
21. Hall, B. J., & Tucker, J. D. (2020). Surviving in place: The coronavirus domestic violence syndemic. *Asian journal of psychiatry*, 53, 102179.
doi: [10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102179](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102179)
22. Yari, A., Zahednezhad, H., Gheshlagh, R. G., & Kurdi, A. (2021). Frequency and determinants of domestic violence against Iranian women during the COVID-19 pandemic: A national cross-sectional survey. *BMC public health*, 21, 1-10.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11791-9>
23. Kofman, Y. B., & Garfin, D. R. (2020). Home is not always a haven: The domestic violence crisis amid the COVID-19 pandemic. *Psychological Trauma: Theory, Research, Practice, and Policy*, 12(S1), S199.
doi: [10.1037/tra0000866](https://doi.org/10.1037/tra0000866)
24. Øverlien, C. (2020). The COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on children in domestic violence refuges. *Child Abuse Review (Chichester, England: 1992)*, 29(4), 379.
doi: [10.1002/car.2650](https://doi.org/10.1002/car.2650)
25. Bright, C. F., Burton, C., & Kosky, M. (2020). Considerations of the impacts of COVID-19 on domestic violence in the United States. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 2(1), 100069.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2020.100069>
26. Roje Đapić, M., Buljan Flander, G., & Prijatelj, K. (2020). Children behind closed doors due to COVID-19 isolation: Abuse, neglect and domestic violence. *Archives of Psychiatry Research: An International Journal of Psychiatry and Related Sciences*, 56(2), 181-192.
DOI: [10.20471/dec.2020.56.02.06](https://doi.org/10.20471/dec.2020.56.02.06)

27. Olding, J., Zisman, S., Olding, C., & Fan, K. (2021). Penetrating trauma during a global pandemic: changing patterns in interpersonal violence, self-harm and domestic violence in the Covid-19 outbreak. *The Surgeon*, 19(1), e9-e13.
doi: [10.1016/j.surge.2020.07.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surge.2020.07.004)
28. Duncan, T. K., Weaver, J. L., Zakrison, T. L., Joseph, B., Campbell, B. T., Christmas, A. B., ... & Bulger, E. M. (2020). Domestic violence and safe storage of firearms in the COVID-19 era. *Annals of surgery*, 272(2), e55.
doi: [10.1097/SLA.0000000000004088](https://doi.org/10.1097/SLA.0000000000004088)
29. Taub, A. (2020). A new Covid-19 crisis: Domestic abuse rises worldwide. *The New York Times*, 6(6).
<https://www.nytimes.com/2020/04/06/world/coronavirus-domestic-violence.html>
30. Uzobo, E., & Ayinmoro, A. D. (2023). Trapped between two pandemics: domestic violence cases under COVID-19 pandemic lockdown: a scoping review. *Community Health Equity Research & Policy*, 43(3), 319-328.
DOI: [10.1177/0272684X211022121](https://doi.org/10.1177/0272684X211022121)